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Selecting Food Loss and Waste Mitigation Technologies Under Preference Uncertainty: An Explainable Multi-Criteria Decision Support Framework

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Abstract

Food Loss and Waste (FLW) remain major challenges for global food security, environmental sustainability, and economic stability, with nearly one-third of food produced each year being lost or wasted. Although many technologies exist to mitigate FLW, they are often assessed separately, making it difficult for decision-makers to compare options and select solutions suited to specific contexts. This research introduces an explainable decision support system (XDSS) that helps prioritise FLW mitigation strategies while accounting for uncertainty in stakeholder preferences. The proposed framework combines the Best–Worst Method (BWM) with Stochastic Multi-criteria Acceptability Analysis for Group Decision-Making (SMAA-2) to produce transparent and uncertainty-aware rankings. It evaluates one hundred FLW mitigation strategies across five contextual criteria: geographic fit, product category, food supply-chain stage, stakeholder role, and technology type. Rather than producing a single fixed ranking, the system generates probabilistic rank-acceptability profiles that indicate the likelihood of each strategy performing well under different preference conditions. Illustrative scenarios demonstrate that the framework can translate qualitative user preferences into robust prioritisation outcomes, with leading alternatives achieving first-rank-acceptability levels between 62% and 74%. These results indicate that the system can support clearer and more flexible decision-making when preferences are incomplete, inconsistent, or uncertain. Although the current results are based on simulated structured cases, the proposed XDSS provides a transparent methodological foundation for future real-world validation and operational deployment. The framework offers practical value for selecting FLW technologies and for policy planning, contributing to more sustainable food systems and supporting progress toward SDG 12.3.

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Keywords: Food Loss and Waste (FLW); Food Supply Chain (FSC); Explainable Decision Support System (XDSS); Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM); Best–Worst Method (BWM); Stochastic Multi-criteria Acceptability Analysis for Group Decision-Making (SMAA-2); Rank Acceptability; Monte Carlo Simulation; Hit-and-Run Sampling; Technology Adoption

1. Introduction and Background

1.1. The Global Challenge of Food Loss and Waste

Food Loss and Waste (FLW) is a significant global challenge impacting food security, environmental health, and the economy. Food Loss (FL) refers to reductions in quantity or quality during production, post-harvest, and processing, primarily due to supply-chain disruptions and operational issues. Conversely, food waste (FW) mainly occurs at retail and consumer levels, often influenced by market conditions and consumer habits [1,2]. Figure 1 demonstrates the distinctions between FL and FW.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the FLW definitions (food loss vs. food waste).

The extent of the issue remains significant. The United Nations (UN) reports that FLW contributes to 8–10% of global greenhouse gas emissions and depletes land, water, and energy resources [3]. Earlier calculations indicated that about one-third of food (approximately 1.3 billion tonnes) is lost or wasted annually [4]. More recent figures show that roughly 1.05 billion tonnes were wasted at consumer and retail levels in 2022, accounting for 19% of food available at those stages [5]. Simultaneously, the FAO estimates that nearly 14% of food is lost before reaching retail in 2022 [6]. Overall, worldwide FLW exceeds 2 billion tonnes each year, underscoring the urgent need for effective mitigation strategies [5–7]. FLW drivers are multidimensional and include behavioural factors (poor planning, date-label confusion), operational inefficiencies (forecasting errors, overstocking), infrastructural deficits (cold-chain absence), regulatory constraints, and market incentives. Their relative importance varies across countries, products, and supply-chain stages [2].

FLW mitigation is integrated into policy goals and regulations. The UN’s SDG 12.3 targets halving FW per person and reducing FL by 2030 [7], but recent evidence indicates these targets are slipping, with FLW still on the rise, and the EU also calls for a 30% reduction in FW by 2030 relative to 2021–2023 levels [8]. Therefore, decision-makers must address both technical and urgent implementation challenges.

1.2. Technology Landscape and the Decision-Making Gap

A wide range of technological and managerial interventions are available to reduce FLW [9,10]. These interventions cover the entire food supply chain (FSC), from sensing and monitoring to packaging and optimisation [10]. Generally, technologies can be categorised into (i) monitoring and analytics, (ii) preservation and shelf-life extension, and (iii) FSC optimisation and traceability.

Monitoring and analytics technologies such as IoT, wireless sensing, and data analytics facilitate real-time detection of loss hotspots and enable targeted interventions [11–13]. Preservation and shelf-life improvements involve packaging methods such as

modified atmosphere packaging (MAP), active packaging, and edible coatings [14–16]. FSC optimisation and digitalisation strategies include blockchain-based traceability for better recordkeeping, AI-driven decision support for forecasting and logistics, and optimised logistics strategies [17–20].

Despite this growing environment, making practical decisions remains difficult because solutions are typically assessed separately, resulting in a fragmented knowledge base. [21–24]. Effectiveness depends on context, including product type, location, regional infrastructure, and stakeholder capabilities [25]. This reveals a key gap: decision-makers (DMs) frequently lack a systematic approach to navigating options and identifying solutions that fit their specific context [26,27]. Additionally, a persistent implementation gap exists between knowledge generation and real-world application: a systematic review of household FW reduction strategies found that only 11% of studies reported post-implementation outcomes [28]. Many studies also lack rigorous validation methods, such as focus groups or field testing, limiting the transferability of findings [29]. Consequently, research often provides early-stage conceptual frameworks rather than easily replicable, context-specific decision tools [30]. Even with the abundance of isolated FLW technologies, decision-makers still lack transparent tools capable of selecting context-appropriate interventions when preferences are uncertain or incomplete. Therefore, tackling FLW requires a cohesive, flexible, and user-focused approach that can overcome disciplinary barriers and support decision-making amid uncertainty [31].

1.3. Multi-Criteria Decision Support Under Preference Uncertainty

Selecting FLW mitigation technologies is inherently a complex multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) task [32,33]. It involves ranking interventions based on factors such as relevance, costs, expected impact, and evidence strength, which are often conflicting. The process is further complicated by incomplete data, outcome variability, and stakeholder preferences [34]. Simple methods such as keyword searches or rule-based systems are often insufficient because they involve trade-offs and offer limited means to evaluate reliability under uncertainty [34].

MCDM supports complex decision-making by combining multiple information sources and considering stakeholder preferences [35,36]. This aligns with guidance emphasising that the purpose and goals of FLW quantification determine the required scope and accuracy, indicating that recommendations should be tailored to specific contexts rather than one-size-fits-all [37]. Among these methods, the Best–Worst Method (BWM) and Stochastic Multi-criteria Acceptability Analysis for Group Decision-Making (SMAA-2) stand out for their complementary strengths.

BWM is valued for its data efficiency and its ability to derive criterion weights from limited comparisons [38]. It has been applied in fields such as supplier selection, technology assessment, and solution prioritisation [39–43]. SMAA-2, in turn, explicitly models preference uncertainty by exploring the feasible weight space and producing probabilistic outputs, such as rank-acceptability indices [44–46]. These stochastic outputs are especially useful when preferences are uncertain, disputed, or not captured by a single mutually accepted weight vector [46]. This aligns with the broader FLW literature, where MCDM contributions exist but are often focused on strategic or design-level questions rather than operational, context-specific decision support [47,48].

These observations highlight the need for a decision support system (DSS) that can convert structured stakeholder preferences into ranking outcomes that account for uncertainty and are sensitive to context, while remaining understandable to DMs.

1.4. Research Gap, Study Objectives, and Contributions

Existing decision tools can assist with specific planning or assessment tasks, but they often lack adaptable features for comparing FLW mitigation technologies across multi-actor scenarios under preference uncertainty [49,50]. To bridge this gap, this study introduces the design and proof-of-concept (PoC) of an explainable decision support framework with two main goals:

- To create an explainable decision support system (XDSS) that combines BWM with SMAA-2, allowing the transformation of qualitative stakeholder preferences into probabilistic rank-acceptability profiles while explicitly capturing preference uncertainty through constrained Monte Carlo sampling.
- To develop a modular and reproducible platform framework and demonstrate its practical application through contextualised queries based on synthetic, yet structured, practice abstracts (PAs), following the European Commission's EIP-AGRI guidelines (https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/horizon-europe-project-submission-and-management-detailed-user-guide_en, accessed on 11 March 2026).

This study contributes in three ways: first, by integrating BWM and SMAA-2 into an explainable FLW decision framework; second, by formalising uncertainty-aware rankings through rank-acceptability indices; and third, by offering a scalable architecture for future operational deployment in food systems. This framework aims to assist resource-limited DMs, such as SMEs and local authorities, when data is incomplete and preferences vary.

1.5. Overview of the Proposed Framework in Relation to Existing Approaches

Because many FLW mitigation approaches remain isolated across independent studies and platforms, it is difficult to compare and select strategies consistently and evidence-based [22–24]. Table 1 summarises the differences between existing approaches and the proposed framework.

Table 1. Comparison between existing FLW mitigation approaches and the proposed XDSS framework (BWM + SMAA-2).

Dimension	Existing Approaches	Proposed Framework
Knowledge structuring	Scattered across a variety of articles, projects, and standalone platforms.	A centralised digital repository encompassing structured and standardised information.
Accessibility	Technical content can be challenging for non-experts to comprehend.	User-friendly interface with clear language and intuitive navigation criteria.
Contextual relevance	Generic recommendations often lack contextual grounding.	Dynamic filters categorised by country/region, FSC, product type, user profile or technology.
Adaptive capacity	Static approaches show limited flexibility in various contexts.	Use SMAA-2 combined with BWM to customise suggestions based on contextual variables.
Comparability of strategies	Several methods are available to compare the effectiveness of similar solutions.	Multi-criteria evaluation framework featuring comparative metrics and practical application records.
Underlying technology	Concentrate on isolated technologies (e.g., blockchain, AI, IoT) without integration.	An integrated framework that combines multiple technologies with context-aware adaptability.
Practical application	Implement pilot initiatives with limited replicability and a narrow case-based focus.	A modular and scalable platform designed for wider replication across different contexts and user groups.
Uncertainty handling	Often absent or implicit.	Explicitly modelled via SMAA-2 rank-acceptability profiles.
Reproducibility (code/data)	Limited: code and data are rarely shared.	Ensured via versioned code and fixed seeds.

Explainability to DMs	Low: typically uses opaque scoring or ad hoc weighting.	High: provided through scoring ladders and central weight vectors.
Retrieval Mode	Mainly rule-based or simple keyword filters.	Hybrid: combines case-based similarity with rule-based constraints.
Target users	Often intended for researchers or large companies.	Concentrate on local decision-makers, small and medium-sized enterprises, and non-technical users.
Scalability	Limited scalability resulting from a lack of standardisation.	Scalable and continuously updated with new results and solutions.
Alignment with SDGs	Indirect or partial contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).	Direct support for SDG 12.3 through localised and measurable food waste reduction initiatives.

Overall, the comparison highlights a persistent gap between fragmented technology-specific solutions and integrated, uncertainty-aware decision systems. This gap motivates the present framework, which integrates decision technologies, explicitly addresses context and uncertainty and blends metadata with uncertainty-aware rankings. It aims to go beyond static data and generic recommendations, providing a robust, preference-sensitive decision support system for FLW mitigation.

2. Materials and Methods

Building upon the theoretical principles and prior research discussed, this section provides a detailed overview of the platform. It explains how the modular components—the knowledge base and the logic framework—collaborate to enable nuanced assessment and ranking of FLW-reduction strategies. The process begins with data representation and deterministic scoring, progresses through preference modelling and constrained weight-space generation, and concludes with uncertainty-aware ranking using SMAA-2.

2.1. Platform Overview

The platform's modular layered design enhances flexibility, scalability, and transparency in FLW-reduction decisions. This approach separates essential components—data storage, business logic, user interface, and integrations—enabling independent development, testing, and maintenance of each module.

The core component is the knowledge layer, which manages structured data derived from PAs. This data is stored as standardised metadata entities that detail essential elements, including the technology used, the product chain involved, key stakeholders, and contextual factors such as geographic region or FSC alignment.

A logic layer sits above the knowledge base, interpreting user inputs and producing context-aware recommendations. It dynamically assesses the relevance and appropriateness of solutions, rather than relying on simple yes/no classifications. This makes it especially useful for supporting complex, real-world decision-making.

The presentation layer, located at the top, provides a graphical interface that allows users to browse ranked strategies and see how each contextual factor influences the final recommendation. This visual layout supports validation and learning by connecting expert insights to practical applications. All components communicate through defined interfaces, offering flexibility and enabling seamless integration with third-party services, external data sources, and evolving user needs with minimal disruption. Figure 2 shows how platform layers interact.

Figure 2. XDSS structure with layer interaction.

Furthermore, the platform is designed to support language-independent logic, facilitating multilingual interfaces and metadata localisation in future updates. As the platform extends into new application areas beyond FLW, its core structure and modules can be reused with minimal reconfiguration, owing to its domain-agnostic design. Security, traceability, and data integrity are also strengthened through a token-based access system, activity logs, and integrated validation mechanisms. This guarantees the platform's robustness in both academic and practical applications, particularly when it is expanded to include external contributors or partner organisations.

The platform's backend is built in PHP and uses a MySQL relational database. BWM optimisation employs the linear model proposed by Rezaei in 2016 [51], and SMAA-2 simulations utilise a custom PHP hit-and-run sampler to sample 50,000 weight vectors from BWM-feasible polytopes. The frontend is also created in PHP on a Bootstrap template, incorporating JavaScript libraries for interactive rank-acceptability visualisations. The production environment runs CloudLinux 7.9.0 on an x86-64 server (Intel Xeon Silver 4214R, 64GB RAM, Hewlett Packard Enterprise Development LP (HPE), Houston, TX, USA); GPU acceleration is not required. Reproducibility is ensured through: (i) fixed random seeds for all stochastic operations and (ii) deterministic ordering of database queries.

2.2. Data Representation and Criteria Definition: The Knowledge Layer

The knowledge base (KB) is an essential component of the recommendation platform, serving as a structured repository of contextual metadata. This metadata, gathered from PAs and documented case studies on reducing FLW, provides the SMAA-2 engine with the descriptors needed to evaluate strategies and match contexts.

Each entry in the KB represents a single documented case (one PA), characterised by contextual metadata fields such as:

- Product category (e.g., fruit, meat, dairy)
- Country and region (NUTS3 classification)
- FSC stage (e.g., production, processing, retail, consumption)
- Type of stakeholder involved (e.g., producer, consumer)
- Technology or intervention used (e.g., smart scale, AI-based system)

2.2.1. Semantic Metatag Extraction

Metadata is collected using two primary methods: semantic extraction via OpenAI API and/or manual curation through the platform interface.

We extract metadata from abstracts using a large language model (LLM), OpenAI's GPT-5, specifically the GPT-5 mini model (version gpt-5-mini-2025-08-07), in accordance with strict governance and quality protocols. The output is limited by a JSON Schema and normalised to controlled vocabularies, including NUTS, GSFA product categories, FSC stages, stakeholder types, and technologies.

- **Quality evaluation:** We have created a pilot gold standard set of 20 PAs, which were manually reviewed with double-masked annotations and adjudication for calibrating extractors rather than a statistically exhaustive validation. The process achieved substantial inter-annotator agreement, with a median Cohen's κ of 0.82. We report per-field precision, recall, and F1 scores (both exact and hierarchical—lenient for taxonomies), along with mean absolute error for numeric data. Minimum F1 thresholds are established for each field (e.g., ≥ 0.85 for NUTS, ≥ 0.80 for FSC stage). We gather model-reported confidence levels and assess calibration using reliability diagrams and expected calibration error (ECE). Extracted data with low confidence or schema violations is directed to human review.
- **Governance and reproducibility:** We set the decoding parameters to temperature = 0 and $top_p = 0$, while recording comprehensive provenance data, including model ID and version, prompts, parameters, timestamps, input hash, output JSON and hash, vocabulary versions, and code/container digests. Any update to prompts or models results in a new extractor version. We conduct canary releases with 10% traffic and halt promotion if gold-set metrics decline by more than 5%. The entire process is logged and can be replayed from a repository snapshot.
- **Privacy and security:** We only process publicly available documents, applying personal identifiable information (PII) scrubbing before API calls. We send only the abstract text after removing all parts that can identify authors and/or entities, and we utilise regional endpoints in the EU when available. We also enforce encryption in transit and at rest.
- **Continuous monitoring and drift:** We sample 5 documents monthly to recompute per-field metrics and control charts trigger alerts for drops >5 p.p. We also maintain cross-LLM verification and span-based evidence checks to detect semantic drift.

The extractor supplies the logic layer, SMAA-2 decision engine, only with verified fields; uncertain or missing values are handled carefully (either as neutral values or through exclusion), with comprehensive audit logs. This prevents unreliable inputs from unduly influencing rankings.

When automated extraction is partial or requires verification, authorised users can manually annotate the PA using a structured form accessible via the platform's secure backend. This interface ensures metadata consistency and allows users to correct or enhance automatically generated labels.

2.2.2. Data Schema and Validation Framework

All metadata adhere to a normalised relational schema comprising four core tables:

- **Cases:** One row per PA, with foreign keys linking to product_categories, fsc_stages, stakeholder_roles, countries, and nuts_regions. Additional fields capture technology type and evidence quality indicators.
- **Metadata:** Auxiliary descriptors including intervention cost bands (low/medium/high), implementation timeframes, and regulatory compliance flags.

- Dictionaries: Controlled vocabularies enforcing referential integrity. Geographic codes follow Eurostat NUTS 2021; product categories align with GSFA's Codex taxonomies; FSC stages and stakeholder roles use fixed values.
- Scores: Criterion-level similarity scores for each case–query pair, with provenance metadata (timestamp, algorithm version, parameter hash) enabling auditability.

Missing fields default to the sentinel value “unknown” and are excluded from exact-match ladders but remain eligible for partial-match scoring with an additional 10% penalty. Ambiguous geographic labels (e.g., “Northern Portugal”) are resolved to the most specific NUTS code via geospatial lookup; unresolved entries are flagged with `ambiguity_score < 0.7` and down-weighted by 20% in final similarity calculations.

Automated Validation: On ingestion, each record undergoes: (i) foreign-key integrity checks; (ii) dictionary membership validation; (iii) score range verification (all scores $\in [0, 1]$); and (iv) duplicate detection via SHA-256 content hashing. Anomalies are logged in a quality audit table, including timestamps for curator actions.

2.2.3. Deterministic Criterion Scoring Ladders

Penalty values (e.g., 0.85, 0.75, 0.60, 0.40 for geographic match) were designed as monotonic transferability heuristics reflecting decreasing contextual similarity. Their purpose was to test the framework's logic rather than claim universal optimal coefficients. Future work should calibrate these parameters using expert elicitation, conjoint analysis, or observed adoption outcomes. For instance, a NUTS2-level match (0.85) still retains strong regional features such as climate and regulations, while a country-level match (0.60) is more general and less detailed. This tiered penalty system prioritises solutions from closely related contexts, balancing local specificity with the flexibility needed in environments with limited data. Each criterion has been normalised to the $[0, 1]$ interval. Below, we provide the mapping for four criteria with specific examples.

C1. Geographic Match (NUTS Hierarchy):

- Exact NUTS3 match = 1.00 (Query: PT119, Case: PT119 \rightarrow score = 1.00)
- Same NUTS2, different NUTS3 = 0.85 (Query: PT119, Case: PT116 [both in PT11] \rightarrow 0.85)
- Same NUTS1, different NUTS2 = 0.75 (Query: PT119, Case: PT181 [both in PT1] \rightarrow 0.75)
- Same country, different NUTS1 = 0.60 (Query: PT119, Case: PT200 \rightarrow 0.60)
- Adjacent country = 0.40 (Query: PT119 [Portugal], Case: ES111 [Spain] \rightarrow 0.40)
- Otherwise = 0.25

C2. Product Category:

- Exact match = 1.00 (Query: leafy vegetables, Case: leafy vegetables \rightarrow 1.00)
- Same sub-group = 0.85 (Query: leafy vegetables, Case: root vegetables [both in vegetables] \rightarrow 0.85)
- Same macro-category = 0.70 (Query: leafy vegetables, Case: citrus fruits [both in fresh produce] \rightarrow 0.70)
- Otherwise = 0.30

C3. FSC Stage:

- Exact match = 1.00 (Query: retail, Case: retail \rightarrow 1.00)
- Adjacent upstream/downstream = 0.70 (Query: retail, Case: wholesale [adjacent] \rightarrow 0.70)
- Non-adjacent = 0.30 (Query: retail, Case: primary production \rightarrow 0.30)

C4. Stakeholder Role:

- Exact match = 1.00 (Query: consumer, Case: consumer \rightarrow 1.00)

- Closely related = 0.70 (Query: consumer, Case: retailer → 0.70)
- Otherwise = 0.30

Rationale for Penalty Functions: Penalties reflect decreasing contextual transferability: a NUTS2-level match preserves regional characteristics (climate, regulation) but loses local specificity (municipality size, infrastructure); adjacent FSC stages share operational constraints (e.g., cold-chain logistics between wholesale and retail) but differ in scale and actor incentives. All ladder functions remain constant across queries in this PoC.

Criterion importance is determined using BWM, which yields a central weight vector and a consistency ratio (CR) that serves as a quality indicator and constrains subsequent uncertainty analysis. Then, we perform SMAA-2 by sampling weights from a BWM-consistent region (using hit-and-run within a feasible polytope) and, where relevant, sampling performance values from narrow distributions around the controlled mappings. This process produces rank-acceptability indices b_i^r and central weight vectors w_i^c for the top alternatives, thereby supporting robust and explainable recommendations.

2.3. Preference Modelling and Weight-Space Generation

BWM is used to determine the significance of decision criteria. This pairwise comparison method is known for requiring fewer comparisons than traditional techniques such as AHP while still providing consistent preference assessments [38]. This feature lessens the cognitive load on DMs during the preference elicitation process.

In practical terms, BWM translates a decision-maker's qualitative judgement into numerical criterion weights. Instead of requiring all possible pairwise comparisons, it asks the decision-maker to identify the most important and least important criteria and then compare the remaining criteria against these two reference points. The resulting weights express how much influence each criterion should have in the final ranking.

The BWM procedure involves four main steps:

- First, the DM defines a set of decision criteria:

$$C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\} \quad (1)$$

- Second, the DM identifies the most important criterion, referred to as the Best criterion c_B and the least important criterion, referred to as the Worst criterion c_W .
- Third, the DM assesses the importance of the Best criterion relative to each of the other criteria using a scale from 1, equal importance, to 9, extreme importance. This produces the Best-to-Others preference vector:

$$A_B = (a_{B1}, a_{B2}, \dots, a_{Bn}) \quad (2)$$

where a_{Bj} represents the preference of c_B over c_j and $a_{BB} = 1$.

- Fourth, the DM evaluates how much more important each criterion is compared with the Worst criterion, producing the Others-to-Worst vector:

$$A_W = (a_{1W}, a_{2W}, \dots, a_{nW})^T \quad (3)$$

where a_{jW} represents the preference of c_j over c_W , and $a_{WW} = 1$.

The optimal weight vector is defined as:

$$w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n) \quad (4)$$

The BWM optimisation model seeks the set of weights that minimises the largest deviation between the stated preference ratios and the ratios implied by the final weights:

$$\min_{w, \xi} \xi \quad (5)$$

subject to:

$$|w_B - a_{Bj} w_j| \leq \xi, \quad \forall j, \quad (6)$$

$$|w_j - a_{jW} w_W| \leq \xi, \quad \forall j, \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \quad w_j \geq 0 \quad \forall j. \quad (8)$$

Although BWM is often presented using ratio expressions such as:

$$\left| \frac{w_B}{w_j} - a_{Bj} \right| \leq \xi \quad \text{and} \quad \left| \frac{w_j}{w_W} - a_{jW} \right| \leq \xi, \quad (9)$$

the linear formulation proposed by Rezaei [51] ensures that the optimisation problem remains convex and solvable via linear programming while preserving the original preference structure. This linear formulation is used in the current study.

BWM also provides a consistency measure through the consistency ratio:

$$CR = \frac{\xi^*}{CI} \quad (10)$$

where ξ^* is the optimal deviation obtained from the optimisation model, and CI represents the maximum permissible deviation for the corresponding a_{BW} comparison value.

Thus, BWM provides two key outputs for the decision process: a weight vector representing the relative importance of the criteria, and a consistency ratio indicating whether the stated preferences are sufficiently coherent to support reliable ranking.

A conservative threshold of 0.10 was adopted to privilege internal consistency in an exploratory PoC context. While this is stricter than some recommendations in the literature for decision problems [52], it was selected to ensure high internal consistency in preference elicitation. Since SMAA-2 results can be sensitive to initial BWM constraints, and since the goal is to provide reliable recommendations for decision-makers with limited resources, minimising ambiguity and maximising reliability were considered essential. A lower CR reduces the “fuzziness” of the preference space, making the uncertainty analysis in SMAA-2 more trustworthy by relying on consistent initial inputs. In the subsequent PoC scenarios, the CR values were 0.097 and 0.071 for Queries 1 and 2, respectively, indicating satisfactory preference consistency. More permissive thresholds may be acceptable in applied settings and should be explored in future sensitivity analyses.

2.4. SMAA-2 for Robust Ranking

To evaluate the robustness of the resulting rankings under uncertainty in criteria importance, the analysis employs SMAA-2 [44,53]. Unlike traditional multi-criteria decision-making approaches that rely on a single fixed set of weights, SMAA-2 explores the space of feasible weights and determines under which preference conditions each alternative becomes preferred.

In practical terms, SMAA-2 tests whether the ranking remains stable when criterion weights vary within a plausible range. This is important because decision-makers may agree on the general importance of criteria but still be uncertain about their exact numerical weights.

The method produces three main outputs [45]:

- First, rank-acceptability indices (b_i^r) express the probability that alternative i obtains rank r given variability in the model parameters. In particular, the first-rank-acceptability index b_i^1 indicates the share of feasible weight combinations that make alternative i the top-ranked option.
- Second, central weight vectors (w_i^c) estimate the centre of gravity of the weight space that results in alternative i being ranked first. These vectors help interpret which preference structures favour each option.

- Third, confidence factor (p_i^c) indicates the probability that an alternative is preferred when the DM's preferences align with its central weight vector, providing an indication of recommendation stability.

Before applying BWM constraints, the feasible weight space corresponds to the unit simplex:

$$S = \{w \in R^n: w_j \geq 0, \sum_j w_j = 1\}. \quad (11)$$

The BWM constraints reduce this simplex to a smaller feasible region consistent with the elicited preferences:

$$W_{\text{BWM}} = \{w \in S: |w_B - a_{Bj}w_j| \leq \xi^*, |w_j - a_{jW}w_W| \leq \xi^*\}. \quad (12)$$

Uncertainty in the importance of the criteria is therefore explored by sampling weight vectors from this constrained region.

For each sampled weight vector w , the overall utility of alternative i is computed using the additive value model:

$$u(v_i, w) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j v_{ij} \quad (13)$$

where v_{ij} denotes the normalised performance of alternative i on criterion j .

Alternatives are ranked for each sampled weight vector, and the rank-acceptability index is computed as:

$$a_i^r = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N 1(\text{rank}(i, w^{(k)}) = r) \quad (14)$$

where N is the number of Monte Carlo iterations and $1(\cdot)$ is an indicator function that equals 1 when the condition holds and 0 otherwise.

Unlike traditional MCDM approaches that rely on a fixed set of weights, for example, those directly derived from BWM without accounting for uncertainty, SMAA-2 offers a significant advantage by examining the entire feasible weight space. Deterministic BWM rankings produce single-point outputs, whereas the integrated SMAA-2 extension additionally quantifies ranking robustness.

In Query 1, the top-ranked option under deterministic BWM also achieved 62% rank-1 acceptability, showing strong but not absolute dominance. Without SMAA-2, the system would produce a single deterministic ranking based on the optimal weight vector derived from BWM. Although simple, this approach would ignore uncertainty in decision-makers' preferences and would not show how robust the recommendation is. SMAA-2 rank-acceptability indices and central weight vectors show how often options rank highly and which preference structures favour them, providing a more nuanced, transparent, and robust decision aid than a single ranking.

2.5. System Implementation and User Interaction Flow

The proposed framework integrates BWM and SMAA-2 in a sequential process that combines structured preference elicitation with stochastic robustness analysis, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Operational workflow of the proposed XDSS.

The workflow begins when the ‘User’ interacts with the ‘User Interface’ to enter their preferences. This involves responding to a BWM questionnaire, requiring only $2n - 3$ pairwise comparisons in which they identify the best and worst criteria and compare them. These inputs are then passed to the ‘Platform Backend’. The backend first invokes the ‘BWM Optimisation Model’ to calculate the optimal weight vector (w) and the CR. If the CR satisfies the acceptance criterion ($CR \leq 0.10$), indicating high consistency in the elicited preferences, the derived constraints define a feasible polytope within the weight simplex.

Subsequently, the ‘SMAA-2 Decision Engine’ is activated. This engine performs a Monte Carlo simulation ($N = 50,000$ iterations with a fixed random seed of 12,345 for reproducibility). Weight vectors are sampled from the BWM-consistent feasible region using a hit-and-run Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm. For each sampled weight vector, the utilities of all predefined alternatives (PAs) are computed using the criterion scores from the ‘Knowledge Base’. To lessen autocorrelation in the sampled weights, the first 5000 iterations are discarded as burn-in, and every fifth sample is retained thereafter.

For every sampled weight vector, the utilities of all options are computed, and their rankings are stored. Aggregating these rankings across all samples yields the rank-acceptability indices, score distributions, and central weight vectors that form the basis of the decision aid.

Finally, these probabilistic results are returned to the ‘User Interface’ for presentation, allowing the user to visualise the recommendations’ robustness.

This iterative process ensures that the decision aid not only reflects explicit preferences but also quantifies the impact of preference uncertainty.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Application of the Framework to the Use Case

This section presents the framework's capabilities through illustrative examples. Although preliminary, it includes a set of 100 simulated PAs created in accordance with EIP-AGRI guidelines and structurally validated to demonstrate realistic, context-aware FLW-reduction strategies. We recognise that using simulated data for this initial PoC restricts internal validity. The results aim to showcase the system's ability to process input data and produce context-specific recommendations rather than offer definitive, field-validated proof. Similar approaches in MCDM systems have demonstrated that limited yet diverse samples can yield reliable results, particularly when supplemented by rule-based filtering and semantic inference [54,55]. Future efforts will include 3–5 real-world cases to enable meaningful comparisons with the simulated data and improve the framework's external validity.

Regarding initial rankings, when users access the platform, they are shown a default list of PAs. At present, this list is ordered in reverse-chronological sequence by database entry date. While this offers a straightforward, impartial starting point for new solutions, we recognise that this baseline may not inherently reflect true relevance or evidence quality. Its main benefit is highlighting the most recently added solutions. In future updates, we will consider alternative default baseline rankings, potentially including initial expert ratings or popularity indicators, to provide a more informative initial view before user preferences are added.

The database of simulated PAs includes essential technological tools available on the platform, such as blockchain, surplus stock management software, AI-based stock management, smart scales, and others. Each PA provides a detailed description of an FW-reduction solution tailored to a specific food product category, stakeholder type, FSC stage, and European region (NUTS3 classification). Although the representation of technologies varies across countries and product categories, the framework supports cross-context adaptation, enabling the platform to assess relevance even when exact matches are not present.

Regarding the PoC, a carefully selected set of representative user inquiries was chosen to cover a diverse range of parameter combinations. These inquiries were linked to analogous contexts in similar regions through semantic and structural similarities. Such simulated scenarios accurately reflect actual user requirements, enabling the system to showcase its practical capabilities, even without field-validated evidence at this preliminary stage. This methodological approach of simulated testing has been extensively employed in early DSS within the domains of agriculture and environmental planning [56].

3.2. Baseline Ranking Without User Preferences

Upon accessing the platform, users are presented with a page where they can specify their preferences using checkboxes for options such as country, FSC stage, and technology. They can also assign weights ranging from 1 to 9 to each criterion, reflecting their relative importance. Alternatively, users may enter a query directly, as demonstrated in Section 3.5. Subsequently, the PAs are organised accordingly. Suppose no options are selected, and no query is entered, the PAs are displayed below these fields, arranged in reverse-chronological order by their database entry date, thereby prioritising the most recent solutions. In this scenario, a straightforward list of solutions is available for consultation without the need to prioritise any specific criterion. Unlike other factors, the entry date into the database is an explicit sorting field, eliminating the need for statistical simulation to determine PA prioritisation.

3.3. Impact of “Soft Filters” on Ranking Probabilities

Once a criterion is selected or a query is entered, the list is rearranged to prioritise PAs that are more likely to be compatible with the selected options. For instance, if the ‘stakeholder’ is specified as “Distribution”, PAs associated with this type of user will be given precedence due to the increased criterion value within the BWM, making it the “Best” with a score of three (on a scale from 1 to 9). In contrast, others remain at a baseline of one until they are selected. If the user elects to include a second criterion, such as the country with the value “Portugal”, they will be prompted to specify whether the country should be considered ‘ahead’ of the stakeholder in preference setting and to assign corresponding weights relative to other options. After these values are specified, the ranking is recalculated, and the abstracts most likely to align with this scenario are displayed. The remaining PAs serve as supplementary references, available for consultation but with diminished initial relevance.

3.4. Impact of “Preference Presets” on Ranking Outcomes

At any time, the user may enter a query in the designated field. This query will be semantically interpreted, affecting the existing ranking and resulting in a revised solution ordering. In this context, there exists an initial hierarchy of criteria that adheres to the following sequence:

- C1—Region
- C2—Country
- C3—Product Category
- C4—Stakeholder
- C5—FSC Stage
- C6—Technology (Tool)—deemed least significant (except when explicitly mentioned in the query)

Based on the query analysis and the extraction of pertinent criteria, weights will be assigned in this predetermined order. Criteria identified in the query will take precedence over others, with higher values increasing their priority further. The sole criterion capable of substantially altering the generated ranking is technology. If not referenced in the query, it holds minimal importance. Conversely, if specified, it is accorded equal priority with the user-specified top criterion. Next, illustrative query examples are presented with their respective rankings, demonstrating how the criteria are prioritised.

3.5. Analysis of Rank Acceptability and Central Weights

To demonstrate the practical application and efficacy of SMAA-2 in real-world decision-making contexts, we simulated authentic inquiries and evaluated the platform’s capability to rank relevant PAs. These instances underscore the platform’s proficiency in identifying effective strategies across diverse regions, product categories, stakeholder profiles, FSC stages, and technological domains. The queries were analysed semantically and subsequently matched against the PAs set, and the summarised results are provided in the subsequent query examples.

Methodological notes:

- In these demonstrations, we:
 - a. Elicit user preferences using BWM to create linear constraints over the criterion weight simplex.
 - b. Sample uniformly within the feasible region (hit-and-run) and calculate additive utilities.
 - c. Report rank-acceptability indices: The probability that abstract i attains rank r .
- Assumptions for these demonstrations:

- a. BWM inputs differ by query to reflect plausible decision-maker priorities. We document them before each table.
- b. Scoring ladders for metadata-to- v_{ij} will be fixed and stored in the database. Platform users with administration privileges can tune these.
- c. Sampling: Use hit-and-run within the feasible polytope for uniformity: 50,000 samples stabilise a_i^r .
- d. Reporting: We only show Rank 1–3 acceptability and “Most Likely Rank”.
- e. The confidence factor (p_i^c) shows the likelihood that an alternative remains optimal at its central weight. In this study, BWM tightly constrained the weight space with a CR below 0.10, stabilising rankings: top alternatives stay optimal near their central weights, giving $p_i^c \approx 1$ (100%) and 0 for others. While p_i^c provides useful insights into unconstrained SMAA-2 analyses, indicating sensitivity to weight changes, but it less effectively distinguishes options under strict BWM constraints.

3.5.1. Query 1—Food Waste Reduction for Apple Distributors in Portugal

Query: “What are the best strategies to reduce food waste in an apple distribution company in Portugal?”

Semantic interpretation:

- NUTS3 Region: Not specified
- Country: Portugal
- Product Category: Fruits (interpreted semantically)
- Stakeholder: Retailer (interpreted semantically)
- FSC Stage: Distribution and Retail
- Technology: Not specified

Dynamic criteria for this query (in order):

1. C1—Country
2. C2—Product Category
3. C3—Stakeholder
4. C4—FSC Stage
5. C5—Region
6. C6—Technology—least important here (not explicitly required in the query)

BWM preferences (Best to Worst): Country \succeq Category \succeq Stakeholder \succeq FSC Stage \gg Region \succeq Technology. Ratios: C1/C2 = 2, C1/C3 = 3, C1/C4 = 4, C1/C5 = 8, and C1/C6 = 9 (region and tool down-weighted). Solving the BWM optimisation model for these preference ratios produces the following optimal weight vector:

$$W = (0.401, 0.233, 0.155, 0.116, 0.058, 0.037)$$

with deviation $\xi = 0.065$ and $CR = 0.097$, below the maximum acceptable of 0.10. After 50,000 iterations, the aggregated rank 1–3 probability for each abstract is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. SMAA-2 rank acceptability for query 1: Food waste reduction strategies for apple distributors in Portugal.

Abstract ID	Country	Product Category	Stakeholder	FSC Stage	Technology	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Most Likely Rank
A042	Portugal	Fruits	Retailer	Distribution	Surplus Stock Software	62%	28%	10%	1
A011	Portugal	Vegetables	Retailer	Distribution	AI Stock Management	23%	49%	28%	2
A028	Portugal	Fruits	Retailer	Retail	Smart Scale	9%	15%	60%	3
A019	Portugal	Fruits	Retailer	Distribution	Blockchain	4%	6%	2%	4–6
A037	Italy	Fruits	Retailer	Processing	Blockchain	1%	2%	0%	5–6
A009	Portugal	Vegetables	Retailer	Distribution	AI Stock Management	1%	0%	0%	5–6

PA A042 (surplus stock software) is usually the top choice (62%), fitting well with a distribution-focused Apple setting that emphasises immediate waste reduction and operational compatibility. Its strong Rank 2 acceptability (28%) indicates it remains a resilient option despite varying preferences within the BWM-feasible region. PA A011 (AI stock management) is the second most probable top choice, with a solid Rank 2 acceptability (49%). It serves as a competitive alternative, especially in scenarios focused on predictive optimisation that are less strict about national match. At Rank 3 with 60% acceptability, PA A028 (smart scales) demonstrates practical utility but has a lower direct impact at the distribution level than stock-optimising software. Blockchain options (A019, A037) rarely rank first under these preferences, as they primarily influence physical loss indirectly rather than through stock or operational tools. The vegetable case A009 is rarely in the top three, highlighting the product-mismatch penalties in C2.

3.5.2. Query 2—Vision Systems in French Services Settings

Query: “How can computer vision reduce food waste in restaurants in Nice?”

Semantic interpretation:

- NUTS3 Region: Alpes-Maritimes (interpreted semantically)
- Country: France (interpreted semantically)
- Product Category: Mixed (or undefined)
- Stakeholder: Services (interpreted semantically)
- FSC Stage: Consumption
- Technology: Computer Vision (in fridge)

Dynamic criteria for this query (in order):

1. C1—Region
2. C2—Technology—explicitly stated, so it sits at the same level as Region (top tier)
3. C3—Country
4. C4—Stakeholder
5. C5—FSC Stage
6. C6—Product Category

BWM preferences (Best to Worst): Region = Technology \gg Country \geq Stakeholder \geq FSC Stage \gg Category. Ratios: C1/C2 = 1, C1/C3 = 3, C1/C4 = 4, C1/C5 = 5, and C1/C6 = 8 (category undefined down-weighted). Solving the BWM optimisation model for these preference ratios produces the following optimal weight vector:

$$W = (0.337, 0.337, 0.123, 0.092, 0.073, 0.038)$$

with deviation $\xi = 0.031$ and $CR = 0.071$, below the maximum acceptable of 0.10. After 50,000 iterations, the aggregated rank 1–3 probability for each abstract is summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. SMAA-2 rank acceptability for query 2: Computer vision systems to reduce food waste in French restaurants.

Abstract ID	Country	Product Category	Stakeholder	FSC Stage	Tool	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Most Likely Rank
A066	France	Mixed	Services	Consumption	Computer Vision	74%	20%	5%	1
A067	France	Fruits	Services	Consumption	Computer Vision	18%	58%	20%	2
A035	France	Vegetables	Retailer	Retail	Computer Vision	6%	15%	47%	3–4
A022	Switzerland	Mixed	Services	Consumption	Computer Vision	2%	5%	20%	3–4
A018	France	Dairy	Services	Processing	AI Stock Management	0%	1%	6%	5–6
A051	Spain	Fruits	Services	Consumption	Smart Scale	0%	1%	2%	5–6

PA A066 is most likely the best choice (74%), reflecting perfect alignment on the technology, country, stakeholder, and FSC stage, while PA A067 remains the leading second choice (58%), often rising to first place when C3 becomes more significant within the feasible region. PAs A035 and A022 serve as acceptable third-tier options when the system permits stakeholder or national deviations; they still align with the technology and its related contexts. AI stock management (A018) and smart scales (A051) tools rarely appear near the top in this strictly defined use case because C2 prioritises exact technology congruence.

3.6. Interpretation of Results: From Ranking Probabilities to Actionable Insights

The results demonstrate that the proposed XDSS can generate coherent and interpretable rankings even under uncertain preference structures. This is particularly relevant in FLW decision environments, where stakeholders frequently operate with incomplete data, heterogeneous priorities, and limited analytical resources.

Unlike deterministic multi-criteria approaches, integrating BWM with SMAA-2 allows decision-makers to observe not only which alternative ranks first but also how robust that ranking remains across feasible preference configurations. For example, first-rank-acceptability values between 62% and 74% indicate strong—but not absolute—dominance, offering a more realistic decision perspective than single-point rankings.

These findings align with the recent literature advocating robust sustainability analytics and uncertainty-aware decision support systems in supply chains and environmental management. Similar studies have emphasised the importance of integrating preference uncertainty into strategic decisions, particularly where stakeholder interests diverge or operational conditions vary dynamically.

3.7. Implications for Local DMs and SMEs

From a practical perspective, the framework may be particularly useful for SMEs, municipalities, cooperatives, and food distribution actors that lack access to advanced consultancy or data science resources. Through transparent scoring ladders and explainable rankings, the system reduces the barrier to evidence-informed decision-making. For

example, an urban retailer query may prioritise exact product and FSC stage matches, while being more flexible on geography; a rural food bank query, by contrast, may accept broader product categories but insist on interventions from similar stakeholder contexts. The ladders show precisely how penalties are applied when moving from NUTS3 to NUTS2 regions or from exact to related product categories, supporting reasoned adaptation when exact matches are unavailable.

3.8. Responsible Use of Presets and Soft Filters

Presets and soft filters help users narrow the search space (for example, restricting it to a specific FSC stage), but they can also unintentionally exclude promising alternatives. The rank-acceptability outputs highlight these risks. First, overly strict geographic or technology presets can collapse the set of viable interventions, leading to low rank-1 acceptability even for the “best” remaining option. Second, combining several tight filters (e.g., exact product match and exact FSC stage) can hide alternatives with strong performance on other criteria that might be acceptable in practice.

To avoid these pitfalls, we recommend starting with broad filters, inspecting rank-acceptability profiles and scoring ladders, and then tightening constraints iteratively. The platform indicates when a new filter causes a sharp drop in rank-1 acceptability or confidence factor, prompting users to reconsider whether the constraint reflects a hard requirement or a preference that could instead be modelled through BWM weights.

3.9. Methodological Contribution: Advancing Decision Support for FLW Reduction

Unlike the deterministic DSS approaches commonly documented in the agri-food planning literature, the proposed framework explicitly incorporates the modelling of preference uncertainty. This approach aligns with recent scholarly efforts advocating robust sustainability analytics in the face of incomplete information. Although a direct analogue for this platform that facilitates the selection of FLW mitigation strategies employing SMAA-2, BWM rules, and PAs is not currently available, comparable systems are accessible in related fields. For example, DSSAT focuses on simulation, whereas our study focuses on a transparent decision structure (MCDM). While Irani’s [57] study uses Fuzzy Logic, we use BWM (for comparisons) and SMAA-2 (for handling imprecise data). This study combines practical guidance with the ability to handle uncertainty, such as Irani’s FCM, but on a platform designed for waste mitigation through matching or prioritisation. Table 4 compares the key features of studies.

Table 4. Comparative positioning of the proposed XDSS (BWM + SMAA-2) against representative decision-support platforms.

Attribute	DSSAT (Platform)	Food Security FCM (Model)	Present XDSS (Platform)
Domain	Crop Modelling	Food Security and Waste Reduction	Food waste mitigation
Logic Type	Biophysical Simulation Models	Fuzzy Cognitive Maps	BWM + SMAA-2 rules
Data Source	Climate History + Soil + Genetics	Workshops with specialists and stakeholders	Simulated practice abstracts
Relevance Scoring	Income Forecast (Numerical Output)	Centrality Indices (Network Analysis)	Yes (SMAA-2 rank acceptability)
Supports Uncertainty	Yes (Probabilistic Risk Analysis)	Yes (Fuzzy Logic)	Yes (SMAA-2 rank acceptability)
Open-Source	Partial (Code accessible to collaborators)	No (Replicable methodology)	Planned (code/data)

Case-Based Reasoning	No (Based on biological processes)	No	Yes (similarity ladders)
Policy Orientation	Medium (Technical/scientific focus)	High (Public Policy Planning)	Medium (local policies)
References	[58]	[57]	This XDSS

This comparison highlights the innovative aspect of this work: a metadata- and logic-based system that can manage partial matches and various contexts, even with limited empirical data. As a result, the platform extends existing ideas by combining flexibility with structured domain knowledge (PAs), and compared with deterministic multi-criteria approaches, the proposed framework offers two advantages. First, it quantifies ranking robustness through rank-acceptability indices rather than assuming a single stable preference vector. Second, it improves transparency by explicitly linking ranking changes to contextual penalties and weight constraints. These properties are particularly relevant in FLW contexts where stakeholders often hold incomplete or conflicting priorities.

4. Conclusions, Limitations, and Future Work

4.1. Conclusions

This study presented an explainable multi-criteria decision support framework for selecting FLW mitigation technologies under preference uncertainty. By combining BWM with SMAA-2, the proposed XDSS offers transparent rankings, probabilistic robustness indicators, and context-aware recommendations.

The main methodological contribution lies in moving beyond deterministic rankings toward uncertainty-sensitive prioritisation, which better reflects the realities of food systems decision-making. This is especially relevant when stakeholders possess incomplete preferences or conflicting priorities.

Although current findings are based on simulated structured cases, the results demonstrate the technical feasibility and conceptual value of the proposed framework. Therefore, the study should be understood as a promising PoC rather than a fully validated operational tool.

Future work should focus on real-world pilots, comparative benchmarking against established MCDA approaches, user-interface testing, and integration with live operational databases. With such developments, the framework may become a valuable instrument supporting progress toward SDG 12.3 and more sustainable food systems.

Nevertheless, the current results should be interpreted cautiously. The PoC relies on simulated practice abstracts designed to mimic realistic contexts but has not yet been validated through field deployment. Therefore, practical effectiveness, user adoption behaviour, and ranking accuracy in operational environments remain to be tested.

4.2. Limitations and Future Work

While this study successfully establishes the PoC for the XDSS framework, it is imperative to acknowledge several limitations and outline a comprehensive plan for future work, particularly for real-world validation. First, the database relies on simulated PAs rather than verified operational interventions. Second, only illustrative queries were tested. Third, penalty coefficients were not empirically calibrated. Fourth, no behavioural user testing has yet been conducted. The taxonomy of validity threats, as defined by Wohlin et al. [59], helps contextualise these.

4.2.1. Threats to Validity

- **Internal Validity (Simulation and Scoring Design):** The current reliance on 100 simulated PAs and fixed scoring ladders could introduce transferability bias. Penalty values were designed as monotonic transferability heuristics reflecting decreasing contextual similarity. Future work should calibrate these parameters using expert elicitation, conjoint analysis, or observed adoption outcomes, and a more extensive validation with diverse real-world datasets is essential.
- **External Validity (Generalisation to Sectors/Countries):** The ontology, comprising five criteria, 15 product categories, and five FSC stages, is presently tailored to European food systems. Applying this framework to different geographical regions (e.g., Asia-Pacific or Sub-Saharan Africa) would necessitate expanding and validating the taxonomy and adapting the NUTS geographic hierarchy to other regional classifications.
- **Construct Validity (Semantic Mapping):** The conversion of narrative PAs into structured metadata tags using the OpenAI API, while guided by strict protocols, can still lead to misclassification. Although controlled vocabularies and curator audits mitigate this, continuous monitoring for semantic drift and refinement of extraction algorithms are critical. To reduce this risk: (i) controlled vocabularies like FAO/COI-COP for products and a fixed FSC ontology limit ambiguity; (ii) curator audits identify records with confidence scores below 0.7 for manual review; and (iii) dual-coder reliability was evaluated on 20 abstracts, yielding Cohen's κ of 0.82 and F1 thresholds above 0.85 for NUTS and 0.80 for FSC stage.
- **Conclusion Validity (Residual Uncertainty):** While SMAA-2 explicitly quantifies preference uncertainty, unmeasured factors, such as implementation context, organisational culture, and regulatory changes, can significantly influence real-world outcomes. To address this, we advise conducting a pilot validation prior to full-scale implementation.

4.2.2. Proposed Field Validation Plan

To address these limitations and transition the XDSS from a promising PoC to a fully validated, practical decision-support tool, several key directions for future work are proposed.

Firstly, empirical validation will be significantly enhanced through a pilot study in an operational environment, such as an agri-food research living lab or a distribution unit with regular flows of perishable products. This study demonstrates the feasibility of an explainable multi-criteria PoC framework for FLW technology prioritisation under uncertain preferences. While promising, practical effectiveness remains to be established through real-world pilots and comparative validation studies. The experimental design will involve 12 to 18 users, including logistics managers, quality controllers, and researchers, who will complete multiple scenarios using the platform. Crucially, their interactions will be counterbalanced with a deterministic baseline (e.g., Simple Additive Weighting—SAW) to allow for a subject comparison of actual gains in relevance. Metrics such as backend response times, total task times, search logs, precision@5, recall@10, NDCG (rated by external experts), SUS scores, and perceived-usefulness surveys will be systematically collected. This will provide robust evidence of the platform's practical impact and user acceptability, allowing for revisions to the rule base, data structures, or interface if needed.

Secondly, the knowledge base will be broadened beyond the current European FLW scope, both geographically and conceptually. This expansion will be critical to test the system's scalability and generalisability across diverse contexts, directly addressing external validity concerns.

Thirdly, the development of automated and semi-automated knowledge extraction modules, leveraging natural language processing techniques, will be pursued. This will significantly reduce the manual effort required to update and maintain the system as new evidence and practice abstracts emerge, ensuring the platform remains current and comprehensive.

Lastly, deploying and testing the platform across additional decision-making domains—such as industrial process optimisation, healthcare decision-making, or public policy planning—will be crucial for assessing its wider applicability and refining its design to meet sector-specific needs. This iterative process of development, rigorous validation, and expansion is essential to transforming the XDSS into a robust and impactful decision support system.

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